

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR FINTECH COMPANIES IN BUY NOW PAY LATER SERVICES MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The adoption of a Fintech digital financing facility “Buy Now, Pay Later” has grown rapidly on the international level. Within last five years Uzbekistan has become a promising player in the dynamic Fintech landscape due its fast integration of technology and finance, coupled with initiatives to enhance financial inclusion. And as e-commerce is growing in popularity among local consumers, Fintech players in Uzbekistan market are focusing on BNPL service development through innovation, local adaptation and diversification of their offerings to meet the growing demand for convenient and accessible point of sale financing tool. The rise of Fintech has drastically disrupted traditional consumer lending practices in the country, bringing forth numerous opportunities and challenges that are explained in the paper. Recommendations for Fintech companies willing to run BNPL business in Uzbekistan are presented in the concluding section.*

Keywords: *BNPL, countries in transition, consumer credit, paying by installments, POS financing, credit scoring, household income, Fintech, Uzbekistan.*

Introduction

The last decade of digitalization in the global financial market has been associated with the unprecedented rise of Fintech companies offering drastically new digital solutions to the services previously considered as a prerogative of traditional banks. The concept of paying by installments is not new and of a simple nature, however Fintech companies have transformed it into digital, fast, and convenient solution with a catchy tag “Buy Now, Pay Later” (BNPL). BNPL is expected to reach nearly a quarter of all global ecommerce transactions by 2026 (Purnell, 2024). Furthermore, Grand View Research (2023) predicts that the fastest growth will be observed in the Asian region, including Central Asian countries.

As Uzbekistan continues to develop its digital financial infrastructure and regulatory frameworks, the Fintech industry is poised for further growth particularly in BNPL market.

Methodology

In this research, the integrated SWOT-MLP analysis has been applied to identify opportunities and challenges at three levels—landscape, regime, and niche—within the Uzbekistan BNPL sector. This analysis facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the market and offers recommendations for an effective adoption of BNPL Fintech service the Uzbekistan financial sector.

Under the Multi-level Perspective (MLP) framework, a niche technology development can reach a particular level that will cause a sizable shift in the regime subject to significant pressure from the landscape. For a smooth transition to occur, there are two conditions to be met: an internal condition of a niche development and an external condition related to regime and landscape

pressures, causing either challenges or opportunities for an existing system (Yang and Jung, 2024). Applying both MLP framework and SWOT analysis in close interconnection allows their simultaneous utilization ('integrated SWOT-MLP analysis') for capturing the full picture in the evolving BNPL sector.

Results and Findings

Radical digital transformation of the banking industry and e-commerce growth in the developing parts of the world represent major growth drivers for point-of-sale (POS) financing (McKinsey & Company, 2024). As noted by KPMG (2024) a growing number of consumers rely on and feel confident about BNPL services as e-commerce turnover keeps rising. the total volume of POS financing and BNPL has reached more than 450 million US dollars and with the annual growth of 38-42% it is forecasted to be 1.5-2 billion US dollars (KPMG, 2024).

Installment plans have been growing in popularity in Uzbekistan due to relatively low-income levels, especially among younger generations and inappropriateness of consumer credit instruments of traditional banks for the dominant Muslim portion of the population.

BNPL Target Segment in Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan's young, smartphone-wielding generations are driving the BNPL revolution. The average age of a resident of Uzbekistan is 29 years (World Bank, 2023). So, Millennials and Gen Z, (these, who are 20-35 years old), are the target segment of BNPL. They are comfortable with digital services (mobile banking and cashless payments), view any payment as an experience rather than just a transaction, and BNPL allows them splitting purchases into affordable installments. Moreover, as the majority of the segment are Muslims, BNPL fintech providers offer 'Halal Finance' options.

Within last five years there has been a surge in the number of BNPL players targeting young 'unbanked' Muslims (more than 18 million people) with intensifying competition for the market share. To stand out and gain a dominant market position, BNPL players have to differentiate themselves through innovative solutions, customer-centric approaches, and efficient services before Islamic banks are allowed to enter the market (targeted regulations on Islamic Finance have not been introduced yet).

Fintechs in Uzbekistan BNPL Market

The rapid development of BNPL in Uzbekistan is facilitated mainly by fintech companies, that build their own scoring models to assess creditworthiness of clients, use AI and machine

learning solutions to leverage information from government resources (i.e. gov.uz) and accelerate decision making process.

Though the exact details vary by provider, most BNPL services offered in Uzbekistan have three basic options:

- *Pay Later* in full after 30 days.
- *Pay Later Installments*: 3-4 equal, interest-free installments up to 4-6 months.
- *Finance It*: splitting the cost of large purchases into 24-36 months with low-interest instalment plans.

Financial habits are still being formed in Uzbekistan. For instance, though consumer credit facilities have been offered by conventional commercial banks for a relatively short period of time, retail exposures doubled as a proportion of sector loans over 2018–2023, reaching 32% at end-2023, the retail loan quality is expected to deteriorate in 2024 and 2025 (Fitch Ratings, 2024). The riskier segments - unsecured cash and car loans have accounted for the majority of the recent retail loan growth. Recent regulatory restrictions introduced by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan and aimed at mitigating the risks of overheating in retail lending, make BNPL option even more attractive.

The majority of BNPL providers in the country would like to capitalise on the strong preference for halal products among Uzbekistan's predominantly Muslim population using ‘Halal Klarna’ approach.

Types of FinTech Companies offering BNPL service in Uzbekistan

Homegrown fintech start-ups: Local fintech start-ups are engaged in payments, lending, and investments. Addressing additional consumer and business needs such as payment apps and wallets, and merchant payment solutions.

International fintech firms: Established international fintech firms have launched in Uzbekistan, stimulating competition and helping promote customer adoption.

Banks: Leading banking incumbents have moved quickly to offer digital-only offerings.

Although, the number of Fintechs in BNPL market has grown considerably, there is still an unmet demand in experienced fintech developers, experts, and active proponents of BNPL benefits (KPMG, 2024).

BNPL business model profit is derived from commissions that are paid by merchants (up to 10% due to intense competition among BNPL providers) and mark-ups on POS financing covered by customers (from 0% to 68%). The markup on merchandises includes the percentage of non-returns, currency risks, compensation to investors, and operating expenses. High mark-up level in POS financing mostly due to expensive funding in local and foreign currencies pose some challenges to the wider acceptance of this type of consumer credit. Classic BNPL plans for 3-4 months with no mark-ups for customers are the most popular among the local population.

Fintechs in Uzbekistan BNPL Service Market

BNPL Service Providers with Online Market Places & PoS

uzum nasiya alif nasiya ZOODPAY BUY NOW PAY LATER iTend IMAN SOLFY

Online Market Places with BNPL Service

BILLZ olcha elmakon idea asaxiy sello!

Digital Banks

ANORBANK TBC BANK TENGE BANK Garant bank

Uzum Nasiya and Alif Nasiya are the leading companies in the BNPL sector of Uzbekistan based on gross merchandise volume (GMV). Uzum, however, dominates the market owing to its large investments in growing the own ecosystem (online market place, digital bank, own POS network, and established ties with local and international merchants).

Challenges faced by BNPL Fintechs

Due to the fast acceleration of Uzbekistan Fintech sector in general, and BNPL service in particular, a number of challenges are being encountered. The government should take a lead and responsibility to navigate and address them, as well as promote further acceptance and growth of the Fintech industry.

Government and Regulation

The key government institutions in Uzbekistan’s transforming financial sector are the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Agency of Perspective Projects (e-commerce regulation), and the Fintech Association of Uzbekistan.

While Uzbekistan does not have a dedicated regulatory framework for BNPL, there is a set of rules for non-banking entities that include e-commerce, micro-lending and consumer protection. As KPMG (2024) states, the regulatory framework is also constantly changing with the current

emphasis on startups' interests. Such constant changes may hinder growth and limit opportunities for Fintech companies.

However, as the BNPL adoption rate in Uzbekistan is increasing, the government should take new measures to regulate the field and increase trust in Fintech. The introduction of a special regulation on BNPL may bring reassurance to consumers, both using BNPL or those who have not tried BNPL services. Evolving regulation can also substantially impact the operations of BNPL startups, requiring them to comply with changing legal requirements while maintaining customer trust and transparency.

Increasing Consumerism among younger generation

BNPL option can make it dangerously easy for young low-income households to spend beyond their means and, consequently trap them in an unbearable circle of debt. Young people can benefit from BNPL, but at the same time they should fully understand the consequences and avoid blaming BNPL later. As Allchin (2023) emphasizes, it is essential for BNPL providers to control that their advertisements are not misleading to consumers. BNPL Fintechs should make it clear especially to young consumers that BNPL is a form of credit rather than a convenient option to finance online purchases.

Competition with Traditional banks

Older generations still prefer to rely more on conventional financial services provided by commercial banks. Banks are well equipped to compete with BNPL and meet the needs of customers: more experience, well-established relationships with consumers and merchants, and trusted brands. Another valid concern for BNPL Fintechs is the absence of consumer loans' credit history base, for example the majority of Gen Z representatives in Uzbekistan have barely used traditional credit products in the past. So, all BNPL players have the task of creating and developing this base in a very short period of time.

Consumer Behavior Shifts and Economic Fluctuations

Due to changing economic conditions and shifting financial priorities, BNPL companies must remain attuned to consumer needs and preferences, as they directly influence demand for BNPL services. Economic uncertainties, high inflation can affect consumer spending habits and repayment capabilities. BNPL startups must establish robust risk assessment mechanisms to mitigate potential defaults and manage financial risks effectively.

Opportunities faced by BNPL Fintechs

By addressing the above stated challenges in a timely and effective manner BNPL providers in Uzbekistan can build strength by utilizing the following unique opportunities in the market.

Game-changer in Uzbekistan market

BNPL is bringing unbanked populations into the mainstream economy – younger generation with no or bad credit history, and Muslim population that needs Halal financing products. So, the flexibility with the lack of interest, offered by BNPL, are particularly alluring, making it the fastest-growing payment method in Uzbekistan.

Win-win solution for consumers and merchants

BNPL offers customers financial flexibility and a convenient checkout process, while merchants gain higher sales turnovers, larger order values, decreased acquisition costs, greater brand recognition, and customer loyalty. So it is expected that BNPL will be an appealing consumer credit financing tool in the future as well.

Innovation and Technology Integration

Startups can explore new approaches to partnerships with merchants, loyalty programs, and tailored solutions for different customer segments to stay competitive. Investing in application of advanced technologies (AI and data analytics) can enhance risk assessment and streamline processes, improving the user experience and increasing the level of customer loyalty.

Education and Awareness

Ensuring financial literacy and educating consumers on responsible usage of BNPL services can foster trust in BNPL providers, encourage sustainable financial behavior, and support the sector's further development.

Discussion

By fostering collaboration among the FinTech businesses, traditional financial institutions, government agencies, and stakeholders, a robust sustainable system can evolve through leveraging collective expertise and resources. However, late payments and losses for BNPL in Uzbekistan need to be studied to better understand the socio-economic impact of this sector development.

Conclusion

Buy Now Pay Later Services are drastically changing Uzbekistan's consumer retail lending landscape, offering a win-win scenario for both consumers and retailers, that needs to be properly regulated to ensure general trust in Fintech. With flexible and customer-friendly approach, BNPL empowers previously excluded consumers to participate in the credit economy, boosting their purchasing power, and driving market expansion.

By understanding the drivers of BNPL acceptance among consumers and its strategic benefits, BNPL service providers and retailers can gain significant advantages. At the same time, by proactively addressing the mentioned above potential challenges and promoting responsible borrowing, stronger customer relationships and sustainable growth of their businesses can be achieved.

REFERENCES

1. Accenture (2022) Can banks grab the buy now, pay later opportunity?, Available at: <https://bankingblog.accenture.com/can-banks-grab-the-buy-now-pay-later-opportunity>
2. Aidala, F., Mangrum D., and Klaauw, W. (2023) "Who Uses "Buy Now, Pay Later"?" Federal Reserve Bank of New York Liberty Street Economics, Available at: <https://libtystreeteconomics.newyorkfed.org/2023/09/who-uses-buy-now-pay-later/>
3. Allchin, L. (2023) Opportunities and Challenges for Buy Now Pay Later Providers in the UK: Navigating New Regulations and Building Trust, RFI Global. Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/opportunities-challenges-buy-now-pay-later-providers-uk-navigating>
4. Cornelli, G., Gambacorta, L., and Pancotto, L. (2023) Buy now, pay later: a cross-country analysis, BIS Quarterly Review. Available at: https://www.bis.org/publ/qtrpdf/r_qt2312e.htm
5. Fitch Ratings (2024) Uzbek Banking Reforms Gain Traction but May Face Delays. Available at: <https://www.fitchratings.com/research/banks/uzbek-banking-reforms-gain-traction-may-face-delays-25-03-2024>
6. Forbes (2023) "Sooner Or Later, Regulators Will Focus On Buy Now, Pay Later". Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/davidbirch/2023/09/08/sooner-or-later-regulators-will-focus-on-buy-now-pay-later/?sh=63ccdc136b8f>

7. Grand View Research (2023) Buy Now Pay Later Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Channel (Online, POS), By End-use (Retail, Automotive), By Enterprise Size, By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2023 – 2030. Available at: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/buy-now-pay-later-market-report>
8. KPMG Caucasus and Central Asia (2024) Fintech: B2C Payments, POS Financing and BNPL in Uzbekistan. Available at: https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/uz/pdf/2024/Fintech%20UZ_Payments_POS%20Financing_BNPL-final.pdf
9. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Non-Bank Credit Institutions and Microfinance Activities, Available at: <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6906701>
10. Layne, R. (2022) Buy Now, Pay Later: How Retail's Hot Feature Hurts Low-Income Shoppers. Available at: <https://hbswk.hbs.edu/item/buy-now-pay-later-how-retails-hot-feature-hurts-lower-income-shoppers>
11. McKinsey & Company (2024) What is fintech? Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-is-fintech>
12. Nilesh, S. (2023) Challenges and Opportunities: The Evolution of Buy-Now-Pay-Later Startups in India. Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/challenges-opportunities-evolution-buy-now-pay-later-startups-s>
13. Ooi, K.-B., Cham, T.-H., Tan, G.W.-H., Al-Emran, M. and Tang, Y.-C. (2024) “Guest editorial: The dark side of FinTech: unintended consequences and ethical consideration of FinTech adoption”. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 42 No. 1, pp. 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-02-2024-619> Available at: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJBM-02-2024-619/full/html>
14. Purnell, M. (2024) Global Buy Now, Pay Later Market: 2024-2028. Juniper Research. Available at: <https://www.juniperresearch.com/research/fintech-payments/ecommerce/buy-now-pay-later-research-report/>
15. World Bank (2023) The World Bank Data Uzbekistan. Available at <https://data.worldbank.org/country/uzbekistan>
16. Yang, J., Jung, S. (2024) Harnessing FinTech for Sustainable Finance in Developing Countries: An Integrated SWOT–Multi-Level Perspective Analysis of Mongolia. Sustainability. *Research Gate*, May 202416(10):4102. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380587143_Harnessing_FinTech_for_Sustainable_Finance_in_Developing_Countries_An_Integrated_SWOT-Multi-Level_Perspective_Analysis_of_Mongolia